

PHILOLOGY

THE NORMATIVE PRINCIPLES AND THE RULES OF TRANSLATION

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Abstract

General translation theory explains the concept of translation norms, which are used to evaluate translation quality. Translation linguistics includes both theoretical (descriptive) and normative sections. Theoretical sections of translation linguistics (i.e., linguistic theory of translation) examine translation as a means of interlingual communication, as an objectively observable phenomenon that can be described and explained. Normative sections of translation linguistics, based on theoretical studies of translation, formulate practical recommendations aimed at optimizing the translation process, facilitating and improving the quality of translators' work, developing translation evaluation methods, and training methods for future translators.

Key words: translation, translators, machine translation.

Translation as a kind of spiritual human activity existed in the late antiquity and had always played an important role in the history of cultures of separate peoples and in the world culture in all nowadays. From the middle of the XX century (after the World War II) the translate activity in all its varieties acquired unprecedented scope thanks to growing intensively of international contacts. That's why our century is called the "Century of Translation". [1]

The history of translation acquaints us with the existence of two tendencies or two types two of transmission of foreign text, which perform quite contrast as regards to each-other. They are:

1) The translation which based upon the tendency of literal reproduction of the language of the original in damage of common sense and the language which is to be found translated.

2) The translation which is based on the aspiration to reflect the spirit, the sense of the original and to observe the demands of native language.

The example of the first type can serve some translation of the Bible to the Greek and Latin languages, and many other languages. The translation of the Arestotel's philosophy works and etc.

The second type of translation more often had been used in the works of secular character (Cicerone). Today translation has become one of the fastest-growing professions. This is because of the rapid rise of multinational businesses and of the use of electronic communication: the volume of translation texts (letters, contracts, emails, instruction manuals, books, computer software's promotional and training videos) has increased incredibly. These texts need to be translated.

Translators usually work from their second language into their native language. So, to be a good translator you should have an excellent command of your native language. [3]

As for machine translation there are some lacks. First of all MT is based only on structural linguistics. Undoubtedly MT from time to time requires additional correction. MT as we guess is implemented with the help of computer programmers. That's why it is just based on certain reserve of "memory" of the computer. As we know machine can neither think nor realize. It must be pointed out that computer performs only that sphere of job, which is laid in its memory by men. Here we see, translation is believed to be a complex phenomenon, touching upon the whole set of elements in both languages. As to machine translation there were some instances when the translation didn't tend itself to automatical process. Translation requires active work of mind, research for linguistic means, choice among possibilities of translation, high stylistic skills. All these cases approach to a highly professional level both in Simultaneous translation and Consecutive translation.

Variety meanings in translation

In semiotics we distinguish three types of meanings. In order to understand these meanings one must proceed from words because words are the bearers of meanings. For example, the word стол, masa (table) refers to a certain piece of furniture; the word (it), собака (dog) to a certain type of animal, etc. It is clear that not all the language signs (words) name things or living beings, but they refer also to actions and processes (as ходит-getmək, говорит-danışmaq), to qualities as больной- хəстə, длинный-uzun, to such notions as причина, связь- əlaqə as well. Subjects, processes, qualities; the phenomena of objective reality expressed

by language signs are called the referents of the signs, the relation between a sign and its referent is called the referential meaning (референциональное значение-ilk mənə). One must know that the referent of the sign is not a separately taken, single individual subject, thing, quality, process, but whole class of them. If a concrete thing, process, quality is meant, in this case we deal with denotation. For example, we may compare table as a piece of furniture and Отойти от стола-Masadən kənar dur. In the first sentence the table is a word with referential meaning, in the second it is denotation of the word table.

We use language, which is a system of signs, and we are not indifferent to these signs in the process of the communication. We express our subjective attitude to these referents expressed by the signs. We may compare Russian words башка и голова, глаза и очи, спать и дрыхнуть, украсть и спереть, baş və kəllə, gözlər və baxışlar, yatmaq və mürgüləmək, oğurlamaq və əkmək where the words express one and the same referents, but different subjective relations. These subjective (emotional, expressive, stylistic) relations are called pragmatic relations and the meaning – pragmatic meaning. [5]

One must not forget that not any sign exists in isolation; any sign functions as a component of a certain sign system. Therefore, any sign is in complicated and multifarious relations with other signs of sign system. For example, the Russian word стол and Azeri word masa is in definite relation with the words мебель-mebel, обстановка- düzülüş, стул-stul, кресло-yumşaq (qollu) stul, etc., in different types of relations with the words деревянный-taxta, круглый-dairəvi, накрывать-süfrə açmaq. The relation of a sign to other signs in the same sign system is called intralinguistic relations and the meaning-intralinguistic meaning.

The semantic structure of the sign is composed of three components-referential, pragmatic and intralinguistic meanings and they are all interconnected and interdependent. Which of these meanings are conveyed from the text of the SL to the text of the TL? First of all, the referential meaning for it expresses the accumulated experience of the whole language community to a less degree pragmatic meanings because, though we recognize one and the same thing in the same form, still subjective attitudes to them differ completely. The least transformable is the intra-linguistic meanings, it is because that in the process of transformation the intra-linguistic meanings of the SL are substituted with those of the TL. We even may speak of non-transformability of the intra-linguistic meanings. The transformation of these three meanings mainly depend on the type of the text. In the texts where we deal mainly with factual information the main attention is paid to transformation of the referential meanings, but in the text with conceptual information pragmatic meanings take the advantage.

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